

THE REALITY OF THE ASSESSMENT PROCESS IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION SESSION UNDER THE COMPETENCY BASED APPROACH

Aissa Elhadiⁱ

Dr., Professor Lecturer,
University of Djelfa, Algeria

Abstract:

If the assessment is considered a part of the teaching and learning process, it is necessarily to integrate and associate into it, it's also considered as a detector for the shortcomings and helps to diagnose the imbalances and fluctuations that can occur during the learning process and help to recover them in normal and regular bases. In this way, we can exploit the student's mistakes or shortcomings in conceiving the methods of taking care of them as a positive and important element in diagnosing and correcting these shortcomings. This occurs because the educational system is dedicated to the nation's aspirations, and devotes its cultural and social choices seeking perpetual mobility to find suitable forms for the formation of generations. Social upbringing also will make them effective citizens capable of carrying out their social, economic and cultural roles.

Keywords: assessment process, physical education, competency based approach

1. Introduction

The educational sector occupies an important position due to the influences it has on society, which aims to achieve progress in all social aspects; cultural, economic and other fields. Therefore, we found that the educational field is a center of interest to all countries without exception, with different degrees, as these countries are making great efforts to achieve the desired progress, despite the different philosophies, objectives and social systems. Algeria, like other countries, has paid great attention to the educational

ⁱ Correspondence: email elhadi_aissa2000@yahoo.fr

sector through focusing on the curricula, teaching methods, teacher training programs and educational guidance. Among the concerns, the educational terminology that emerged in several countries in the second half of this century, especially the last quarter of it, has made major changes to the concept of assessment according to teaching techniques and methods. Thus, education becomes part of a process that leads from the goals to the results - the assessment - through appropriate activities, means and tools.

Assessment is a part of the teaching and learning process. It is integrated within. It is also an indicator of the shortcomings in diagnosing the imbalances and fluctuations that can occur during the learning process and helps to achieve them in a regular manner.

In this matter, taking advantage of the student's errors or shortcomings in conceiving the methods of ensuring them is a positive and important factor in diagnosing and correcting these shortcomings.

Finally, the multi-role assessment is an opportunity and a tool to change the relationship between the learner and the teacher on the one hand and between the teacher and the parents on the other.

2. Research Problem

The educational system dedicated the nation's aspirations and its cultural and social choices, and seeks in a sustainable movement to find suitable ways to brought up generations in a social upbringing to make them active citizens able to carry out their social, economic and cultural roles. So, the movement of the educational system finds its source in the need of preserving the national cultural heritage and the religious and social values that characterize Algerian society through its historical. Also to explore the future with scientific and technological requirements, on the other hand, to prepare generations to become jealous citizens to their identity and able to raise the various challenges imposed by globalization. The Algerian school is no exception to this rule, thus it is required to renew its curriculum, which differed from what it was in the past. It has now been adopted to achieve competencies at all levels, which appear in the behaviors and actions of the student when faced with the problems encountered in his educational journey and daily life as well. Furthermore, the design of the programs that have been applied in our institutions goes back to define their objectives and determine and their contents to previous decades in addition to the Algerian society's profound political, social and cultural changes that changed the social philosophy and opened up legitimate aspirations for progress and development, this is what made Algeria up to

the challenge so, it adopted the competency based approach in teaching and included it through a multi-year plan in the educational system. Where the Algerian system has adopted competency based approach in its curriculum for all subjects, physical education and sports received a share of this change through the construction of new curricula since 2003. To remind, the prior curricula was adopted in the construction of the educational goals as a basis to guide the process of education and learning of what seemed then The effectiveness of the approach to educational goals, but teachers didn't give relative importance to this approach, which was often limited to the formal and administrative aspect at the beginning, and the new curriculum came to enrich this first experiment.

The competency based approach which is an extension to the goals based approach depended on preparing the pupil fully and adequately to cope with the everyday life challenges and different phenomena, It should be noted that this will not be possible until after reaching what is required in this school of life as accuracy, harmony and homogeneity between the educational programs, and the nature of the pupil dealt with on one hand and between these contents and the reality of the field on the other hand, so the suggestion and the application of the assessment process to the fullest and in a fair way as a process. The physical education should be on a continuous evaluation because the latter is necessary for the development and modification, which can be confirmed by the success or failure of the curriculum of physical education in achieving their goals on time in accordance with the objective plans, thereby ensuring their development.

Therefore, the researcher believes that the process of assessment is highlighted through its reality and its application on the ground during the physical education session under the competency based approach "Some secondary schools of Tisimsilit" by asking the following questions:

2.1 Main question

1. Has the assessment process under the competency based approach been properly applied during the physical education and sports sessions?

2.1.1 Sub-questions

1. Does the assessment of pupils upon the results obtained during physical education classes take individual differences into account?
2. Is the current allotted timed for physical education sufficient to assess all pupils at the same activity during the session?

2.2 Research Hypotheses:

2.2.1 General Hypothesis

The assessment process is correctly practiced during the physical education session under the competency based approach.

2.2.2 Partial Hypotheses

1. The assessment of students based on the results achieved during the course of physical education take individual differences into consideration.
2. The current allotted time is sufficient to assess all pupils at the same activity during the physical education session.

3. Study Objectives

1. Highlight the equal opportunities for students by taking into account individual differences.
2. Giving the subject its true value by evaluating the students' efforts.
3. To show that the current allotted time is insufficient to evaluate all students in the same activity during the session.

4. Significance of the Study

The new reforms came in the modern curricula presented in the competency based approach, which relied on the modern assessment, from here came the importance of this research, which we evaluate the accepted assessment, which we are trying to detect the positive and negative aspects in order to reach a real evaluation taking into account all aspects of physical, educational and Individual differences.

5. Study terms

5.1 Assessment

Is a descriptive method to a phenomenon, a situation, a curriculum, a program, etc. to show the strengths and weaknesses and the extent of the assessment. It includes the collection and analysis of information, and then the judgments on the value of things, persons or subjects, whether in their advantages or disadvantages.

Assessment in the field of physical education includes assessment of the performance of pupils and players and then judgments on this performance in light of

specific considerations to the performance, and includes the assessment of the amount of proceeds that can be accessed through the practice of the program

The assessment of physical education adds to the judgments of programs, curricula, methods, training methods and capabilities.

5.2 Physical Education

It can be defined as the group of activities, skills and arts that the program includes in the various stages of training. It aims to provide students with the skills and tools that help them in the learning process. They can rely on personal experience and self-practice. This means the necessary mechanisms to make them in a position where they can observe, listen, discover, understand, innovate, express and report.

5.3 Competency based approach

Is an approach based on declared goals in the form of competencies gained by the contents which depend on physical activities and sports as a cultural backbone as well as the gains of the previous learning stages, and the approach which focuses on the student as a center of interest in the learning process.

These gains turn into abilities, knowledge and skills that enable the student to prepare for new materials in a context that serves what is expected of him at the end of a particular learning stage.

6. Review of the literature

A. Rahmouni El Hadj Study (2010-2011: The extent to which social harmony is achieved through the practice of physical and athletic education in light of the new educational reforms (competency based approach).

Research problem:

The research problem was about the following main question:

- Does the practice of physical education in the context of educational reform contribute in achieving social harmony among the secondary stage students?

Research Objectives:

- To know if there are statistically significant differences between practitioners and non-practitioners in the total degree of social compatibility.
- To know whether there are statistically significant differences between practitioners and non-practitioners in the sub-dimensions of social compatibility.

Research Methodology:

Descriptive approach to suit the problem of the research.

Population and research Sample:

The research sample included 80 secondary school students from some of the high schools in Medea

Results of the study:

After presenting and analyzing the results obtained at the end of the research:

- There are statistically significant differences between practitioners and non-practitioners of physical education in the social class in favor of practitioners.
- There are statistically significant differences between practitioners and non-practitioners of physical education in the sub-dimensions of social compatibility in favor of practitioners.

From the above, it is clear that the general hypothesis is correct, which claims that the practice of education under educational reform contributes in achieving social compatibility among the secondary stage students.

B. Khenish Youcef's study: A Supplementary Note to the Achievement of the Master's Degree in Education Sciences, branch: Educational assessment of the Curriculum (2005-2006) entitled: The difficulties of the assessment in middle schools and teachers strategies to overcome them.

Research methodology:

The researcher relied on the descriptive approach, which enables to prove or deny hypotheses. The descriptive approach can collect information and give a quantitative formula and helps to arrange and classify this information according to the variables that guide the research, which allows for organized interpretation and scientific analysis.

Results:

1. There are difficulties for evaluation especially when evaluating the behavior of the student.
2. Difficulties in building and using different assessment methods and not allocating time to review them.
3. There are no differences in terms of difficulties in assessment according to the gender.

7. Application side

7.1 Chapter I: Research Methodology and Procedures

The researcher used the descriptive approach because of its relevance to the nature and objectives of the current study.

7.1.2 Sample

The sample of the study was selected from some of the secondary schools of Tisimsilit, where we chose five secondary schools. The sample was 1561 pupils.

7.1.3 Research Tools

7.1.4 Questionnaire

We have identified the necessary axes for the form depending of many theoretical studies, sources and references related to the study. The questionnaire included two axes.

7.1.5 Survey

We conducted an exploratory study on a sample of 52 teachers in order to determine the extent to which the researchers accepted the questionnaire. We have revised the unclear questions and submitted this questionnaire to a group of arbitrators. All statements have been granted by the arbitrators' agreement.

The researcher used Alpha to verify internal consistency.

Dimensions	Factor Link	Stability	Honesty
The first axis	0.96	0.97	0.98
The second axis	0.86	0.92	0.95

Table 2: Stability grades in the Alpha Cronbach method

7.1.6 Statistical Processing:

The researcher calculated the data of this study by using the percentage degree.

7.1.7 Chapter 2: Presentation, analysis and discussion of results

The first axis

Question No 1: *“Does the assessment applied by the teacher take into account the individual differences between you?”*

Answer	Repetition	Percentage
Yes	717	45.93%
No	844	54.06%
Total	1561	100%

Table 10: Shows the percentage of students' answers to the first question from the first axis

Results analysis: The results show that 54.06% of the students believe that the teacher does not take into consideration individual differences during the evaluation process with the expression “No” meanwhile 45.93% of students said “Yes”.

The researcher considers that non-observance of individual differences by the teacher when applying the assessment process during the session may be due to the lack of time or to the large number of students or perhaps lack of available facilities within the institution.

Question 5: *“Does your teacher’s ignorance to individual differences affect your willingness to attend the session?”*

Answer	Repetition	Percentage
Yes	1089	69.76%
No	472	30.23%
Total	1561	100%

Table 5: Shows the percentage of students' answers to the fifth question from the first axis

Results analysis: The results show that 69.76% of the students believe that the non-observance of individual differences during the assessment process leads the students to not practice physical education. This percentage reflects the expression "Yes" while the ratio of 30.23% represents the answer “No”.

The researcher considers that non-observance of individual differences by the teacher when applying the assessment during the lesson is considered a negative factor through the boredom of students from this position and this leads to the lack of desire to practice the session and this is considered an obstacle to students.

The second axis:

Question 3: *“Do you think that the current allotted time is sufficient to assess all of you in denying the activity applied during the session?”*

Answer	Repetition	Percentage
Yes	644	41.25%
No	917	58.74%
Total	1561	100%

Table 3: Shows the percentage of students' responses to Question 3 of the second axis

Results analysis: The results show that 58.74% of the students believe that the time allotted is insufficient to assess them all in the same activity. While 41.25 % said “No”.

The researcher considers that the current time allocated for the physical education session is not enough to assess all students in the same activity due to the large number of students in the session doesn't fit with the time allocated.

Question No. 6: *“Do you think that the allocated time during the session makes you achieve your educational and physical goals?”*

Answer	Repetition	Percentage
Yes	679	43.39%
No	882	56.50%
Total	1561	100%

Table 6: Shows the percentage of students' responses to Question 6 of the second axis

Results analysis: The results show that 56.50% of the students believe that the allocated time of the class does not allow them to achieve their educational goals. While 43.39% of them said “Yes”

The researcher considers that the current allocated time of physical education doesn't allow to achieve the goals of the activity and display the full physical talents and this is due to the time allocated to the activity, that means, students are restricted by the time of activity applied by the teacher.

The physical education teacher suffers when applying the assessment process during the lesson and this is due to several factors, including the large number of students studying in one class.

The teacher suffers from the time allocated to the physical education session which doesn't go along with the students' number.

8. Suggestions

In the light of the study findings, and previous studies, the researcher can make the following suggestions:

- The possibilities and means of assisting the assessment process within the institution should be provided.
- Reduce the activities in which the student is being tested.
- The timing of the physical education session should be reconsidered.
- The quality of selected activities during the physical education should be adapted to the number of pupils within the group.
- The professor of physical education must devote more time to the assessment process during the lesson.

9. Conclusion

Assessment is the compass that directs each work to the right destination and shows the success of any work accomplished. It works to control and correct the shortcomings as well as the positives of any work. It also works to control the total proceeds for the educational process in general and physical education especially in terms of profitability and achievement of desired goals.

Since the evaluation process is a crucial process because it determines the success or failure of the student, we did this research in which we tried to address some aspects of this educational process we dealt with the time allocated to the physical education session as well as the difficulties found by the researcher during the session. Finally, a number of suggestions were put forward to give attention to the teacher by providing him with all the assistance requirements for the assessment process.

In the end, we hope that we have achieved even a little bit of understanding of the subject of our research from all aspects, and if we have left an aspect of it, this is characterized by scientific research continuity, we ask our colleagues students to complete the path in this area.

References

1. Salah al-Din Muhammad Abu Nahia "Educational Measurement" Bibliotheca Alexandrina 1994
2. Tayeb Nateem Sulaiman, Zaatout Abdel Rahman, Qawal Fatima, "Competency Approach: Pedagogic Concepts in Education" Dar Al Amal Printing, Publishing and Distribution, September 2004
3. Farid Haji, "The Approach to Competencies as an Integrated Pedagogy", Educational Achievement Series, No. 17, 2005
4. Mohamed Boualak, "Introduction to the Approach to Education by Competencies", Book Palace, Blida 2004
5. Mohamed Sobhy Hasayin, "Evaluation and Measurement in Physical Education, C.1, Arab Thought House, Cairo, 1979
6. Laland-A-vocaboulaire de la philosophie puff, Paris, 1959

Aissa Elhadi
THE REALITY OF THE ASSESSMENT PROCESS IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION
SESSION UNDER THE COMPETENCY BASED APPROACH

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).